

Three dimensional geological modelling in the context of the PLANMAP project.

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Three dimensional geological modelling (Wellmann and Caumon 2018) is widely employed in the mining and oil industry for creating 3D geometrical representations of geological structures (sedimentary bodies, faults, folds etc...), which can then be used as a sound basis for performing any kind of physical simulations, as for example modelling fluid-flow in porous media. The applicability of these techniques have been for long restricted to studies on Earth because of the sparsity of surface and subsurface data available for small bodies and solid planets.

This perspective has been progressively improving during the last years thanks to an overall increase in quality and variety of products that have become available, suggesting that, not only it is now possible to approach geological studies in a more detailed manner, but also that 3D modelling techniques might soon become a valuable tool for developing and refining the conceptual models behind the formation and the evolution of geological features.

In this perspective, the PLANMAP project is exploring the application of three dimensional geological modelling in the context of planetary sciences, trying to extend surface information to the subsurface. Both implicit and explicit modelling approaches have been evaluated in real scenarios via open source tools and proprietary software on the Moon by using Chang’e III Yutu’s rover GPR data (Xiao et al. 2015), on Mars by exploiting SHARAD radargrams (Putzig et al. 2018) and structural data on the Crommelin crater (Pozzobon et al. 2019), on comet 67P where only surface information was used to produce a comprehensive model of the inner layering (Penasa et al. 2017), and on Mercury in the Rembrandt basin (Semenzato et al. 2018).

Results of this preliminary investigation show that these techniques can indeed be applied also in the planetary context. Although the resulting models suffer of several limitations due to the scarcity of observations, they provide a way of visualizing the structures undergoing investigation with a numerical representation that is inherently coherent in all the directions. The models make it possible to extract additional quantities related to the involved volumes or other geometrical parameters.

Inferring the subsurface from an extremely limited set of observations is a challenging task for the planetary scientists. Any three dimensional model of a geological body not only is required to honour measurable constraints but should also respect all the previous geological knowledge about the formation and evolution of the body under study. The development of such conceptual models and their subsequent integration into three dimensional representations cannot be decoupled. Such approach will be one of the key by which our understanding of geological processes on solid planets and small bodies will improve.